

MODERN RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF FOOD SAFETY AND ITS CURRENT
ISSUES

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Abstract. One of the actual problem is rational use of secondary raw materials in modern food shortage. To solve these problems, scientists have to conduct a lot of practical and theoretical research. Currently at the level of Uzbekistan there are many company in the food sector, in particular the practice of rational use of secondary raw materials in food production. As a result of the complex processing of raw materials in the food industry, a lot of departure could be obtained. Pectin extraction research and apple pomace starch, corn syrup and sunflower turban were carried out in laboratory conditions.

Keywords. Food safety, UNO, safe products, food products, waste, secondary products, threats, pectin, starch, changes.

Anotatsiya Zamonaviy oziq-ovqat taqchilligi sharoitida ikkilamchi xomashyodan oqilona foydalanish dolzarb muammolardan biridir. Bu muammolarni hal qilish uchun olimlar ko'plab amaliy va nazariy tadqiqotlar olib borishlari kerak. Hozirgi kunda O'zbekiston darajasida oziq-ovqat sohasida, xususan, oziq-ovqat ishlab chiqarishda ikkilamchi xomashyodan oqilona foydalanish amaliyotida ko'plab korxonalar faoliyat ko'rsatmoqda. Oziq-ovqat sanoatida texnologik jarayonlar natijasida sarflangan birlamchi xom ashyolarda ko'p miqdorda chiqit olinadi. Laboratoriya sharoitida pektin ekstraksiyasi va olma pomasining kraxmal, makkajo'xori siropi va kungaboqar sallasi bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borildi.

Kalit so'zlar. Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, UNO, xavfsiz mahsulotlar, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari, chiqindilar, ikkilamchi mahsulotlar, tahdidlar, pektin, kraxmal, o'zgarishlar,

Анотация Одной из актуальных проблем является рациональное использование вторичного сырья в условиях современного продовольственного дефицита. Для решения этих задач ученым предстоит провести множество практических и теоретических исследований. В настоящее время на уровне Узбекистана существует множество предприятий пищевой отрасли, в частности практикуется рациональное использование вторичного сырья в производстве продуктов питания. В результате комплексной переработки сырья в пищевой промышленности можно было получить много отходов. Исследования экстракции пектина и крахмала из яблочных выжимок, кукурузной патоки и тюрбана из подсолнечника проводились в лабораторных условиях.

Ключевые слова. Пищевая безопасность, УНО, безопасные продукты, пищевые продукты, отходы, вторичные продукты, угрозы, пектин, крахмал, изменения,

Wholesale trade in agricultural products in our country is rapidly developing in the coming decades.

A large number of enterprises and companies have appeared that are engaged not only in the sale of raw materials and finished products, but also in the processing of these types of goods. In addition, now our country is doing everything for the development of agriculture. Thus, new documents are being adopted to simplify rules for trade in agricultural raw materials. Specialists involved in the wholesale trade of agricultural products must know not only the documents

governing their activities, but also the requirements of the market. For example, the cost of raw materials may change depending on the season, harvest and climatic conditions.

International expert researching on food safety have revealed that a difficult situation has developed in the world and in some of its regions today this problem is considered one of the most urgent and serious threats to the world community.

Trichoderma harzianum- active substance of biological pesticides (fungal fungicides) used in the field of plant protection against various crop diseases.

The antagonist fungus *Trichoderma harzianum* is one of the universal and effective means of biological control of wilting and root rot of many crops, it has a number of mechanisms that allow suppressing the development of pathogens of seed, root and soil infections as well as fruit and leaf diseases.

Physico-chemical characteristics *Trichoderma harzianum* colonies grow well and rapidly on milk agar; in this environment they are always zonal and covered with flocculent aerial mycelium. The back is not painted. The structure and size of spores and phialides differ in different strains.

Impact on pests The behavior of different strains used for plant protection has its own peculiarities.

TECHNOLOGICAL SCHEME OF OBTAINING PECTIN

Pretreatment of raw materials
Hydrolysis and extraction
Filter the extract
Centrifugation
Concentrate the extract
Dissolution of pectin (using ethanol)
Extraction of pectin
Drying

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and the World Health Organization, more than 840 million people in the world, that is, almost one in eight people are currently undernourished, and more than 30% of the world's population are experiencing undernourishing vitamin and mineral substances.

The breaking between a rapidly growing world population and the limited potential for food production growth is the main reason that's why every year the issue of food safety becomes more sharp, deepening in the regions.

At the level of Uzbekistan, there are currently many campaigns in the food sector, in particular the practice of rational use of secondary raw materials in food production. As a result of the complex processing of fruits in the industry, a lot of waste was obtained. Research on the extraction of pectin and starch from apple pulp, corn starch and sunflower bran under laboratory conditions.

There are two different ways to obtain pectin: fractional extraction of pectins and a quick whole extract. The technique of the first method is that the analyzed finely ground plant material is extracted in a water bath with a tenfold amount of 95% ethanol to remove sugars, waxes, etc.

Firstly raw materials brought, pistachio baskets were crushed in laboratory conditions and then they were enzymatically processed and prepared for hydrolysis and extraction. For our experiment, the previously dried and seeded sunflower turban was ground using a coffee grinder.

60 g of crushed dry mass, weighed and sterilized in an oven for 3 hours. 100 g of dry matter, from which the polysaccharide and pectin are isolated. was removed and also placed in an oven for 3 hours for sterilization.

The fungus *Trichoderma* used as an enzyme. Its function is to soften the hard sunflower turbans and speed up their decomposition. The mass was fragmented, the extract was filtered. Then it was centrifuged and concentrated. The pectin is extracted by precipitation with ethanol. The sediment was left to dry naturally.

The sunflower turban fermented by the fungus *Trichoderma harzianum* for 10 days, removed from the thermostat and the liquid part separated from the thick mass using a sieve both samples were left for 24 hours for natural settling in separate flasks. 3 cooled samples of 2 ml, 0.5 ml on top were taken into test tubes. Added 96% alcohol. A precipitate formed in tubes 1 and 2. 450 ml of alcohol poured into a measuring cup, 250 ml of solution No.1 poured on top then it was noticed that a precipitate formed. 500 ml of alcohol was poured into another beaker, 200 ml of solution No. 2 was placed on top, and the phenomenon of precipitate formation was observed. After an hour, the formed precipitates were filtered off separately through a sieve.

Each of the filtered precipitates was placed in 100 ml of 80% alcohol in separate flasks and kept for 2 hours. The precipitated alcohol of liquid is distilled off. The cooled samples of solutions (1-2-) were again filtered through a sieve, the lower part was placed in Petri cups for drying and placed in a thermostat at 34°C for 2 hours.

Flasks 1 and 2 formed a good precipitate. After 2 hours, samples No.1 and No.2 were taken, placed in a thermostat for drying, and weighed on an electronic balance. Sample 1 weighs 1.25 grams. Sample 2 weighed 0.5 g. Sample 1 was dark gray and sample 2 was white.

The dried mass was placed in a glass container and taken out for storage in a dry and normal temperature place.

The precipitate is filtered out from the solutions, the mixture of 95% alcohol and ether is again washed with ether and dried at 85°C. Next the material is placed in a container equipped with a glass filter and filled with an extraction liquid preheated to the desired temperature. Often uses water or 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. According to the second method, 100 g of finely ground test material is placed in a three-liter flask and filled with the same amount of hot water. The contents of the flask are heated to 88...90°C in a water bath, after which was add sulfuric acid to its final concentration of 0.4...0.6%.

The extraction process lasted 60 minutes for 88...90°C. Then, flask is removed from the water bath and cooled rapidly with cold water. Then add distilled water up to 2 l, mix and cool, which is associated with the need to dry and extend the shelf life of pectin-containing raw materials before processing.

REFERENCES

1. Dodayev.K.O., Mamatov.I.M. "Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini konservalash korxonalarining loyihalash asoslari va texnologik hisoblari"- Toshkent "Iqtisod - moliya" 2006 yil. 208 bet.
2. Шахов С.В., Рязанов А.Н., Шубкин С.Ю., Корышева Н.Н., Матвиенко Н.А. Разработка технологии получения пектина на основе ресурсосберегающей переработки растительного сырья // Продовольственная безопасность: научное, кадровое и информационное обеспечение. В 2 ч. Ч. 2.: матер. Междунар. науч.-техн. конф. /Воронеж. гос. ун-т инж. технол. – Воронеж.: ВГУИТ, 2014. – С. 264-265.